

Equilibrium Studies on Binary Complexes of Trivalent Lanthanones with Amino Acids

N. M. PATEL^a, M. N. PATEL, JR.^b and J. D. JOSHI^{a,b}

^aScience College, Bharuch

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120

Manuscript received 3 March 1994, revised 19 July 1994, accepted 22 July 1994

The formation constants of La^{III}, Pm^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes with glycine are known¹. La^{III} and Ce^{III} are known to form complexes with amino acids². Stabilities and thermodynamics of uranyl(II) and thorium (IV) complexes of DL-nor-leucine have been studied³. The complex formation of uranyl(II) and vanadyl(II) with DL-tryptophane have been studied employing potentiometric technique and overall changes in thermodynamic functions have been calculated⁴.

In the present communication Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁵ has been used to determine the stability constants of amino acid complexes of trivalent

lanthanones systematically.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants are presented in Table 1. The proton-ligand stability constant order of the amino acids is as follows : valine > serine $\approx$ threonine $\approx$ methionine < aspartic acid.

The amino acids are bidentate ligands⁶, coordinating from carboxylic acid end after the dissociation of COOH and from NH⁺₃ end with the dissociation of the proton. Thus in case of bidentate amino acid ligands,

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND FORMATION CONSTANTS * OF LANTHANONE-AMINO ACID COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM
Temp. = 25° ± 1°, Ionic strength = 0.2 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand	pK ₁ ^H	pK ₂ ^H		La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}	Gd ^{III}
Valine	9.52	2.23	log k ₁	5.29	5.42	5.60	5.47	5.24	5.10
			log k ₂	4.80	4.86	5.31	4.31	5.04	4.80
Serine	9.02	2.15	log k ₁	4.72	4.86	4.67	4.71	4.89	4.66
			log k ₂	3.97	4.13	4.20	4.21	4.01	4.13
Threonine	9.01	2.18	log k ₁	4.86	4.89	4.90	5.03	4.98	4.64
			log k ₂	4.04	3.98	4.02	4.65	4.40	4.40
Methionine	9.14	2.16	log k ₁	4.86	4.93	4.81	5.13	5.04	4.93
			log k ₂	4.16	4.10	4.47	4.51	4.70	4.38
Aspartic acid	9.63	3.66	log k ₁	5.30	5.72	5.47	5.62	5.89	5.65
			log k ₂	5.01	5.44	5.00	4.87	4.92	5.22

Limits of error ± 0.05.

*Present address : Department of Chemistry, North Gujarat University, Patan-384 265.

ML stands for $M[L^-]$. In case of aspartic acid, the first carboxylic acid group dissociates at low pH. The protons of other carboxylic acid group and NH_3^+ dissociated on coordination with metal ion. Aspartic acid has two negative charges.

The formation constants of trivalent lanthanide amino acid complexes follow the order: $La < Ce < Pr < Nd < Sm > Gd$. There is steady increase in $\log K_1$ values from La^{III} to Sm^{III} , which is due to decrease in size of the metal ion with subsequent increase in ionic potential. The decrease in ionic size of lanthanide ions is not uniform. The decrease in size for Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Pm^{III} , Sm^{III} , Eu^{III} and Gd^{III} is 0.027, 0.021, 0.018, 0.016, 0.015, 0.014 and 0.012 Å respectively. The largest decrease is being observed with the first electron added to each orbital that is in case of Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} . The smallest decrease in size has been observed in case of Gd^{III} . Besides, the charge-size ratio also play an important role in deciding the stability of the complex. Higher the values of the charge-size ratio, greater is the stability of the complex formed. The M^{3+} -size ratios for La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Pm, Sm and Gd are 2.828, 2.960, 2.962, 3.016, 3.064, 3.112, 3.158, and 3.198 respectively. However, $\log K_1$ values of Gd^{III} is lower than the earlier members of the series. The smaller decrease in size of Gd^{III} ion may not be favourable for its higher stability. While higher value of ionic potential is favourable for higher stability. From the observed stability constant values it has been observed that smaller decrease in size is the prime factor for decrease in stability of the Gd^{III} ion. Thus the behaviour of Gd^{III} is abnormal in this series, and this behaviour is known as gadolinium break⁷.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Solu-

tions for the equilibrium study were prepared in double-distilled water. Free perchloric acid and metal nitrate solutions were standardised by acid-base and complexometric methods⁸. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 M using 1 M sodium perchlorate. An Elico LI-10T pH meter was used. Potentiometric titrations were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using 0.2 M sodium hydroxide in inert N_2 atmosphere. The interpretation of potentiometric curves was similar as reported earlier⁹. From the titration data, $\bar{n}_{II}$, $\bar{n}$ and P_L were calculated⁵. The formation constant values were calculated using method of least-square¹⁰ using a Buzeeby HCL PC/XT computer.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. M. N. Patel, Head, Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, for facilities.

References

1. S. N. LARIONOV and I. M. BATYAEV. *Izv. Sibirsk. Otd. Nauk SSSR*, 1962, **12**, 69.
2. H. TRAPMANN, E. BAUMANN and A. ROTHER. *Arch Pharm.*, 1959, **29**, 292.
3. S. K. DHAVAN and R. S. SAXENA. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 87.
4. G. L. SHARMA and R. S. SAXENA. *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1981, **30**, 148.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
6. M. PHILIP, M. N. PATEL, M. P. PEERAZADA and J. D. JOSHI. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 871.
7. H. FLASCHKA. *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1955, 55.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th ed., Longmans, London, 1978, p. 296.
9. C. R. JEJURKER, I. P. MAVANI and P. K. BHATTACHARYA. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 469.
10. P. K. BHATTACHARYA and M. V. CHIDAMBARAM. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3271.